

An overview: Polymer Derived Ceramic (PDC) Coating on stainless steel

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Abstract

Metallic component especially stainless steel exposed highly reactive and corrosive environments such as high temperature oxidation, acidic corrosion, degrade or fail quickly leading to enormous economical loss. Common solution to this problem is either using expensive alloys or replacing corroded parts frequently. Alternatively, applying corrosion resistance coating offers promising way to protect metallic substrate from corrosion and extended their service life. Conventional methods of making coatings include, but not limited to, thermal spraying, welding, electroplating, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [1] and physical vapor deposition (PVD) [2], all of which are high energy consumption techniques. Recently polymer derived ceramics (PDCs) have gained greater attention due to its properties like easy application on substrates of any shape, low temperature processing and the potential to tailor the properties via microstructure and composition design. Pre-ceramic polymers are attractive for coating applications because of their strong adhesion to polymers, metals, and ceramics, which is attributed to the formation of covalent bonds between precursors and coated surfaces. Further, these compounds, in polymeric and ceramic states, possess outstanding protective properties that are necessary for environmental barrier applications [3-6]. A critical thickness exists for polymer derived ceramic coatings. Below this thickness value, the coatings remain intact, dense and adherent. If the thickness exceeds this value, cracking and delamination of the coatings occur during pyrolysis. Different pre-ceramic system with pyrolysis temperature is tabulated in table-1

Table 1
Well-known PDC coating systems.

Precursor systems	Substrate	Temperature	Environment	Reference (Published year)
Polyhydridomethylsiloxane (PHMS)	Carbon Steel/Stainless Steel	600 °C/700 °C	Air	[5] (2009)
Polysilazane	13CrMo4-5 (AISI A182) & X5CrNi18-10 (AISI 304)	700 °C	Air	[6] (2012)
PHPS polysilazane/ ABSE polycarbosilazane	Stainless steel (AISI 304)	1000 °C	Air	[7] (2009)
Polyhydridomethylsiloxane (PHMS)	Stainless steel (AISI 304)	800 °C	Air	[8] (2012)
Polyhydridomethylsiloxane (PHMS)	316 stainless steel	800 °C	Air	[9] (2008)
Polymethoxymethylsiloxane/ Hydroxy-terminated linear dimethylpolysiloxane	Stainless Steel (#1.4301 DIN EN 10027-2)	1000 °C	Argon	[10] (2010)
Polyhydromethylsiloxane PHMS	Stainless Steel 316 (UNS S31600)	800 °C	Air	[11] (2014)

The greatest disadvantage of polymer derived ceramics is the shrinkage of the polymer during pyrolysis, which can be higher than 50% by volume. Residual stresses caused by the high volume shrinkage lead to the formation of defects, cracks or even delamination of the coatings. By adding passive fillers like SiC, BN, ZrO₂, Al₂O₃[7-8] and/or active fillers like Nb, Ti, TiSi₂, Hf [9] the volume change from polymer to ceramic conversion can be significantly reduced. By selecting proper filler particle with thermal expansion coefficient which matches with thermal coefficients of substrate, overcome the limitation of residual stresses. With help of fillers it is possible to generate coatings with additional functionalities like special friction properties, electrical or thermal conductivity or catalytic activity. Table-2 Different fillers and glass with their thermal expansion coefficients[10].

Material	Average particle size	Thermal expansion	Softening point (°C)	Density (g/cm ³)
	d_{50} (mm)	coefficient α (10 ⁻⁶ /K)		
BN	0.7	3.5–4	–	2.25
Si ₃ N ₄	0.6	2.5–3.5	–	3.2
ZrO ₂	1	9–13	–	5.7
Glass 8472	9.7	12	360	6.7
Glass G018-198	9.9	9–10	444	6.6
Glass 8470	3.3	10	570	2.8
Glass G018-311	3.1	10	770	3.8

For this, different polysilazane systems, ceramic fillers and glass additives were selected and investigated as coating materials. A processing route which includes pre-treatment of the steel substrates, preparation of the coating slurry, application of the composite coating and thermal treatment in air were studied from different researcher's. The investigations show that the pre-treatment as well as the application of a polysilazane systems on steel substrates are very important to achieve well adherent composite coatings. One of them was double layer coating (i.e. bond coat and top coat), increases the adhesion of the composite coatings and further acts as diffusion barrier against oxidation during the pyrolysis step of the coating system. The critical coating thickness of the coating systems can be increased up to 100 μm , if the polysilazane and filler systems, their volume fractions and the processing parameters are tailored and optimized. Cyclic oxidation tests showed that the coating system protects steel against oxidation up to 800 °C. The results of various studies confirm that the combination of PDCs with tailored fillers and glass systems enable the processing of thick, dense and crack-free composite coating systems. Furthermore, the double coatings can be processed in air, leading to an efficient process. These coatings are suitable as protective coatings at medium temperatures, e.g. for exhaust systems, waste incineration plants, metal or glass casting and for applications in the chemical industry.

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